

1 **Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: Phc1.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of *Phc1* as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in human embryonic
11 stem cells.

12 Citations

13 1. Chen, L., Tong, Q., Chen, X., Jiang, P., Yu, H., Zhao, Q., Sun, L., Liu, C., Gu, B., Zheng, Y. and
14 Fei, L., 2021. PHC1 maintains pluripotency by organizing genome-wide chromatin interactions of the
15 Nanog locus. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), p.2829.

16 2. Chen, L., Tong, Q., Chen, X., Jiang, P., Yu, H., Zhao, Q., Sun, L., Liu, C., Gu, B., Zheng, Y. and
17 Fei, L., 2021. PHC1 maintains pluripotency by organizing genome-wide chromatin interactions of the
18 Nanog locus. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), p.2829.